

Microfluidic-assisted engineering of multilayered microcapsules for 3D stem cell culture

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ABSTRACT

Regenerative medicine has increasingly made use of adult stem cells in the last years (1, 2). Micro-engineering a biomimetic three dimensional structure provides a realistic approach for stem cell niche studies, and further translational applications. A promising approach for engineering artificial stem cell niches is provided by high-throughput microfluidic technologies. In this work, a droplet-based microfluidic-assisted encapsulation device for the generation of multi-layered cellular structures on demand using alginate and Puramatrix is presented. This novel technology is based on gravity-driven flows, passive mixing principle and a gelation system where the use of a double laminar oil flow where only one contains the cross-linking agent allows both the uniform gelation of the inner core and the continuous generation of a stream of cross-linked hydrogel beads. The soft consecutive coating of the inner core with a second and a third layer without exposing the encapsulated cells to external forces that might reduce their viability represents a promising technology towards 3D stem cell encapsulation. Furthermore, we demonstrate the suitability of the presented technology for encapsulation of stem cells by using human Mesenchymal Stem cells (hMSCs) and human Hematopoietic stem cells (hHSCs). Preliminary results demonstrate a niche model capable of mid-term culture of primitive hHSCs in a microfluidic environment. Therefore, the presented method could apply for the artificial reconstruction of the stem cell niche components as an efficient approach to study stem cell behaviour in vitro under controlled conditions, opening a wide field of potential applications within uTAS for 3D cell culture and tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: Microfluidics, Microencapsulation, Droplet technology, Tissue engineering, Stem cell niche

1. INTRODUCTION

Regenerative medicine has increasingly made use of adult stem cells in the last years due to their therapeutic potential^{1, 2}. It has been previously reported that three-dimensional (3D) cell culture structures promotes many biological relevant functions not observed in 2D monolayer cell culture³. Therefore, the best approach to mimic the native stem cell microenvironment would include microengineering 3D structures able to allocate stem cells.

Approaches for 3D-organized cell culture have included a myriad of scaffold-free systems^{4, 5} and scaffold supported systems^{6, 7}. Stem cell maintenance studies in these structures have also been performed in suspension or in spinner flask, resulting in large heterogeneity in spheroid size⁸, and hanging-drop techniques that provide some control over the spheroid size but lacks of aggregated generation control^{9, 10}.

Previous work from our group reported several methods used for the generation of multicellular aggregates to accommodate stem cells¹¹. It was concluded that most of the reported methods to date were lacking of stability on the template¹² or control on the geometry of the cell constructs¹³. Even when using scaffolds, cell location inside the droplet could not be determined as most of the studies used single bead culture or co-culture spheroids^{14, 15}. Hence, there is still a need to develop a technology able to create highly complex, and well-controlled 3D dynamic environment for stem cell culture in order to mimic in vivo systems.

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Microfluidic techniques offers the opportunity to encapsulate cells into templated matrices in a controlled manner. Some studies have used laminar co-flows for the generation of multi-layered beads^{16, 17}, however these methods were not suitable for the generation of double layered alginate-alginate beads while requiring a complicated set-up.

Our group already reported a technology to produce a double layered hydrogel bead able to accommodate adult stem cells where controlled generation of the structure geometry, composition and cell distribution was achieved¹¹. This technology has been improved by including an additional third layer in order to be able to better mimic the stem cell niche environment and recapitulate more complex biological systems.

In the presented droplet-based microdevice, hydrogel droplets are produced by hydrodynamic focusing techniques and gelled by the circulation of the droplet between two laminar flows, one containing the cross-linking agent. Generated droplets are consecutively coated by two hydrogel layers by synchronizing droplet production rates.

The presented technology permits the rapid extraction of the generated cellular constructs for immediate washing and culture, limiting the time exposure of the cells to the cross-linking agent. Additionally, it does not requires the use of any external force to handle and mix the droplets, resulting in a specially mild and suitable method for the encapsulation of adult stem cells. This three-layered hydrogel bead generator represents a promising technique able to provide optimal requirements for 3D multicellular stem cell culture and to recapitulate in vitro the in vivo stem cell niche environment opening a wide range of possibilities within microTAS and tissue engineering.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials/Chemicals

Mineral oil (Sigma Aldrich) was used as the main oil carrier. Sudan red dye (Sigma Aldrich) was used to color the oil containing the cross-linking agent and visualize the interface between the two main carrier oil flows. Alginic acid sodium salt powder (Sigma Aldrich) was used to prepare the alginate solutions. The aqueous phase was composed of deionized water unless otherwise stated. Puramatrix (Becton Dickinson) solution was prepared at the corresponding concentrations by sonication of the gel for 30 minutes at 30C. Cresol red dye (Sigma Aldrich) was used as Ph. indicator for the inner core droplet. Acetic acid (Sigma Aldrich) was used as the cross-linking agent. Nano-calcium carbonate powder was purchased from Skyspring Nanomaterials and used following the vendor protocol.

2.2 Cell assays

Phosphate Buffered Saline PBS was acquired from Cultek. Calcein-AM (0.1ug/ul) and Dapi 10mg (200ug/ml) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). HLA-DR V450 was purchased from Becton Dickinson, US. Phosphate Buffered Saline PBS was acquired from Cultek, Spain

Bone Marrow CD34+ cells were purchased from Lonza. Human Mesenchymal stem cells were purchased from DSMZ. The cell line was cultured in DMEM (Biowest, France) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum. Cells were cultured and used from passages 2–6 in a 37°C humidified incubator with 5% CO₂. Trypsin-EDTA (0.25%), phenol red was acquired from Thermo Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA).

2.3 Microfabrication

The microfluidic devices were designed using Solidworks CAD (Dassault Systèmes) software. A computer numerical control (CNC) program was then created using Mastercam (CNC Software Inc.), according to the microfluidic circuit design and dimensions.

The outline of the device was extracted from a PMMA plastic sheet (MacMaster-Carr) using a Laser engraver (Universal Laser Systems, VLS 6.30). The plastic cut out was then taken to a CNC machine (HAAS Super Minimill), where the microfluidic circuit was created based on the Mastercam program. Milling conditions – milling direction, spindle speed, feed rate – were optimized for surface quality. Finally, fluidic ports were created using a drill press (Ellis).

The PMMA device was sealed with a self-adhesive pouch (Opko diagnosis). Main channel dimensions are displayed in Figure 1 The device was connected to open barrels of 10 ml disposable plastic syringes (BD biosciences) via silicone tubing (ID 1.1mm O.D. 2.16mm) (Fisher scientific). The driving force used for the experiments was gravity, so liquid pressure on the microdevice was controlled by the heights of the open syringes. Pieces of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) tubing (OD 2 mm) (Cole Parmer) were used to interface the reservoirs to the chip.

2.4 Microscopy

Fluorescence images were acquired using inverted laser scanning confocal microscopy (LSM510 META, Axiovert RT 200M, Zeiss, Germany) equipped with an environmental chamber maintaining the cells under physiological condition, using the laser lines 405 nm and 488 nm.

For all other experiments, a Motic Stereoscope (Motic) and Moticom 2.0 software (Motic) were used. Droplet sizes were analyzed on screen using Image J software.

2.5 Research methodology

The presented device schematic and operational process is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: a) Schematic of the three layered hydrogel bead generator and snapshot of a recorded video comprising (from top to bottom), the hydrodynamic focusing generation of the inner core, the passive mixing process for the formation of the first layer and the passive mixing process for the outer layer b) CAD design of the manufactured platform.

First, alginate droplets containing calcium carbonate nanopowder are generated by hydrodynamic focusing using gravity to drive pressure. The droplets then travel through a meandering channel containing two laminar oil flows. By the addition of acetic acid to the second laminar oil flow continuous phase, calcium ions are released after droplet formation by the diffusion of the acetic acid across the oil interface. The platform is designed so that the second oil flow containing

the cross-linking agent has a double function for both cross-linking and adjusting the droplet production rates of the generated droplet without affecting the gelation process.

The so generated droplets are then passed by a second inlet where a stream of second sample layer alginate droplets are generated in a synchronous way. Hence, when the inner core droplet reaches the area of the second droplet production, the two droplets (one gelated and another ungelated) passively mix along the meander, generating a double layered hydrogel bead. Then, the generated double layered droplet continues travelling along the meander, leading to the gelation of the outer layer. When the double layered gelated bead reaches the third inlet layer where a third droplet is generated, a three layered structure is generated again using the same mixing principle.

The passive nature of the mixing principle underlying this construction process enhances the suitability of these resulting structures for accommodating stem cells.

Preliminary experiments demonstrated that both the gelation process and the three layered bead generation technique are suitable for the encapsulation of living cells by using human Mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) and human Hematopoietic stem cells (hHSCs). Double and triple cell laden structures were generated, washed and cultured in order to assess encapsulated cell viability.

This mild three layered bead generation technique allowed us to encapsulate the cells in the middle layer with high viability using alginate (sample 1)- alginate (sample 2)- alginate (sample 3) scaffolds and alginate (sample 1)- alginate (sample 2)- Puramatrix (sample 3) scaffolds.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Premixed aqueous samples containing alginate (1,6 wt %) and Calcium carbonate nanopowder (1 wt %) were prepared as sample 1, 2 and 3. When using alginate as Sample 3, Puramatrix (0,3% v/v) was prepared following the vendor instructions. The second oil was prepared by adding glacial acetic acid to a pre-dyed Sudan red mineral oil (0.5% v/v).

First characterization studies were run by varying the height of the oil 2 and using alginate as a scaffold in all layers. Adjustments of the samples flow rates were performed so that the inner core produced was synchronized with the second and third droplet produced. Measurements of the three droplets constituent layers production rate were performed as well as its mixing efficiency by areas (droplet 1 with droplet 2 and droplet 2 with droplet 3). Also the total mixing efficiency of the device resulting from the measurements of the number of droplet 1 droplet 2 and droplet 3 merged were measured respect droplet 2 production rate and droplet 3 production rate. These preliminary experiments showed the capacity of the geometry for the suitable synchronization of the flow rates so that the desired three layered bead can be produced.

Figure 2 a) Preliminary characterization of the three layered device. Operational conditions for a inner layer, middle and outer layer 1,6% wt alginate, b) CFC imaging of a three layered bead containing fluorescent latex beads on the middle layer.

A set of experiments using fluorescent latex beads to be added to the middle layer sample was also performed. The objective of this trial was both to assess the stability of the layers and the approximate shape of the collected beads. Figure 2b shows pictures taken in a confocal microscope of three layered beads containing latex fluorescent beads on sample 2 (middle layer).

Further characterization was performed using Puramatrix on layer 3 of the structure. Experimental procedure and parameter analysis was performed as described before. In order to be able to visualize the layers with the on-site experimental setup, cresol red dye was added to the inner core, while keeping non-coloured alginate for the middle layer and Puramatrix (optically transparent) for the outer layer.

Figure 3 shows the results of this characterization. These results showed that higher droplet production rates favors the three layered bead production. Optimal conditions could be determined for which 100% of the produced inner core droplets were coated by a second and a third layer of hydrogel sample.

Figure 3 a) Characterization for the three layered device operational conditions using low droplet flow rates (droplet production rates below 38 droplets/min) and b) high flow rates (droplet production rates below 50 droplets/min) c) Comparison between the total number of three layered beads for droplet production rates in a) (left) and b) (right).

Shapes of the final structures varied between a concentric shape or a non-concentric structures due to the slight differences that occurred on the scaffold gelation points at the time of the passive mixing. The following results on viability and cell encapsulation capacity, suggested that they were not affected by the shape of the resulting final three layered structure, while still being a three layered spheroid.

3.1 Cell encapsulation and culture

The suitability of the presented method for cell encapsulation was demonstrated by accommodating living human Mesenchymal stem cells (hMSCs) into the middle layer.

Prior to resuspension in PBS and mixture in premixed alginate emulsification, human Mesenchymal stem cells were routinely cultured and trypsinized. We used two cell density ranges, 3 and 15× 10⁶ cells/mL. The generated cell laden structures were collected and washed to remove residual acid. Calcein-AM (0.1 μM) which fluoresces green upon the reaction of intracellular esterase and stains live cells; and DAPI 0,1 M which binds to the DNA of dead membrane compromised cells were employed to visualize the distribution of living and dead cells right after encapsulation.

Beads containing 15x10⁶ cells /ml hMSCs on the middle layer were produced, collected and observed under confocal microscopy in order to assess its stability (Figure 4). Results of the life dead assay demonstrated that the encapsulated cells remained with high viability, therefore demonstrating the device suitability for stem cell encapsulation.

Figure 4: a) : Life dead assay on a three layered bead using 15x10⁶ hMSCs/ml in alginate 1,6% wt. for the middle core, and empty alginate 1,6% wt. for the middle and the outer layer. From top left to bottom right, four different configurations of shape for the three layered beads b) Z-stack confocal imaging of a life dead assay on a three layered bead using 15x10⁶ hMSCs/ml in alginate 1,6% wt. for the middle core, and empty alginate 1,6% wt. for the inner and the outer layer.

An additional experiment was performed encapsulating 3x10⁶ cells/ ml hMSC in both the inner and the outer layer to complete the viability assay in the three layers (Figure 5). The material on the outer layer was set to be Puramatrix 0,3 % v/v in order to assess the viability of the middle layer encapsulated cells in alginate with Puramatrix as an outer coating layer. The calcein-DAPI assay was performed following the same protocol as before, demonstrating high cell viability after encapsulation.

Figure 5: Life dead assay using 3x10⁶ hMSCs/ml in alginate 1,6% wt for the inner core, empty alginate 1,6% wt for the middle layer and 3x10⁶ hMSCs/ml in 0,3% v/v Puramatrix on the outer layer. a) bright field microscopy image b) Life dead assay.

From the operational point of view, it was concluded that as long as both oil flow rates are initially equilibrated to co-flow equally along the main meander, heights of sample 1, 2 and 3 can be fine-tuned to achieve a situation of close to full synchronization to obtain a three layered bead generation.

Longer crosslinking times, i.e. extended exposure of the encapsulated cells to the acidic environment on the meander or at collection, or higher concentrations of acetic acid on the second oil would result in a lower cell viability (data not shown). However the presented technique able to minimize the acid exposure together with the low mechanical stresses that cells experiment to be embedded in this three layered construct, constructs presented high cell viability after encapsulation. Furthermore, the cells were clearly compartmentalized in a middle layer and remained; the shape of the three layered droplets remained unchanged after gelation and no leakage of cells after encapsulation was observed. Considering that cell viability could be increased by adjustment of the hydrogel's mechanical properties, this method could represent a technology not only for living cell encapsulation but also for long term culturing of cells in highly controlled microgel matrices in the near future.

In order to test this technology as a tool for stem cell maintenance and culture, human Hematopoietic Stem cells hHSCs were encapsulated in the inner core of the three layered device. For this experiment, 5×10^6 hHSCs/ml were in alginate 1,6% wt. empty alginate was used for the middle core, and Puramatrix 0,3% was used as the outer layer. Cells were enclosed in the inner core of the structure as it was considered the most critical condition due to the double cover of hydrogel. The generated structures were produced as described before.

Collected beads were exposed for 20 minutes to DMEM containing mineral oil and introduced in the incubator in order to accelerate the outer layer gelation. All the samples were afterwards washed with PBS twice before adding culture media. Generated structures were cultured and imaged at 24/48/72 hours and then over a week using DMEM media 10%FBS. No media change was performed during the 7 days of cell culture.

FITC CD34+ which signals hHSCs green and DAPI 0,1 M which binds to the DNA of dead membrane compromised cells were employed to visualize the distribution of hHSCs living and dead cells right after 24,72 and 1 week of cell culture.

Beads containing hHSCs in the inner layer were produced, collected and observed under confocal microscopy in order to assess its viability (Figure 6).

Figure 6: a) : FITC CD34+-DAPI assay on a three layered bead using 5×10^6 hHSCs/ml in alginate 1,6% wt. for the middle core, and empty alginate 1,6% wt. for the middle and PM for the outer layer. From left to right, three samples of beads after 24,72 and 1 week of cell culture-

Results of the FITC CD34+-DAPI assay demonstrated that the encapsulated cells could be cultured after being generated in the presented device at least for a week and moreover remained with high viability without the use of any additive on the media or supporting cell, therefore demonstrating the suitability of the presented technology for human stem cell encapsulation.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we present a droplet-based microfluidic platform for the generation of three layered hydrogel beads suitable for adult stem cell encapsulation. This novel technology is based on a passive mixing principle and a gelation system where use of a double laminar oil flow where only one contains the cross-linking agent allows both the uniform gelation of the inner core and the continuous generation of a stream of cross-linked hydrogel beads. The soft consecutive coating of the inner core with a second and a third layer without exposing the encapsulated cells to external forces that might reduce their viability represents a promising technology towards 3D stem cell encapsulation.

Furthermore, we demonstrate the suitability of the presented technology for encapsulation of stem cells by using human Mesenchymal Stem cells (hMSCs) in the middle layer. Moreover, hMSCs were also encapsulated in the inner core as a test proof of its application as a method for the artificial reconstruction of the hematopoietic stem cell niche components. The presented device represents an efficient attempt to engineer stem cell niches *ex vivo* in a multilayered three dimensional matrix, and a suitable approach to study stem cell behavior *in vitro* under controlled conditions. Therefore, the presented device is a valuable and unique tool towards understanding stem cell behavior in 3-dimensional environments.

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